

UNDERSTANDING THE RIVALRY AMONG AFRICAN PIVOTAL STATES FOR A PERMANENT SEAT IN THE UNITED NATIONS SECURITY COUNCIL AT THE END OF THE COLD WAR.

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Abstract

: This paper argues that Nigeria's continental rivals in the quest for a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council can challenge Nigeria's aspiration. The paper further argues that Nigeria's challengers appear better placed to clinch the seat in the event of an expansion of the UN Security Council. The central research question of this paper is why Nigeria's quest for a United Nations Security Council seat may not be realized. Using both primary data and secondary sources, the authors analyzed the often neglected continental angle of the ongoing debate over the need for African representation. The authors contend that pivotal states, such as Egypt, Kenya, and South Africa, posed a serious challenge to Nigeria's aspiration for a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council.

Introduction

Nigeria's quest to secure a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council (UNSC)² is being challenged at the regional level, as other key pivotal states, such as Egypt, Kenya, and South Africa, have also launched heavy political campaigns for the prestigious position of permanent membership of the UNSC.³ In its earlier resolution reached in Ezulwini, Swaziland, the African region had agreed on a common position popularly referred to as the Ezulwini Consensus, in which they unequivocally demanded two permanent seats with all accompanying privileges, such as the right of veto, including five non-permanent seats.⁴

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³Henceforth, the United Nations Security Council will be referred to as the UNSC.

⁴Ikponmwonsa, O., Osaherumwen, S., Mugadam Mahamat Mugadam, and Sidibe Oumar. "Nigeria-South Africa Rivalry in Quest for regional power status: from material potential to un security Council membership." *Вестник Российского университета дружбы народов. Серия: Международные отношения* 20, no. 1 (2020): 147-157.

⁵Mbara, George Chimdi, Nirmala Gopal, Stanley O. Ehiane, and Hosea Olayiwola Patrick. "Re-evaluating the African Union's Ezulwini consensus in the reform of the United Nations' Security Council." *Journal of African Union Studies* 10, no. 1 (2021): 53-70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jau.2021.01.070>.

While many other interest groups from other parts of the world, such as the Group of Four (G4)⁵ and the Uniting for Consensus Group (UCG)⁶, criticized the African common position for being overambitious in their agitation, the African states, on the other hand, have also ardently criticized all other groups' positions for what they claimed as their 'anti-African' positions, since most of their resolutions marginalized and sacrificed the interest of African states for what they termed as 'merely concessionary purposes.'⁷ Thus, African states claimed that the positions of other groups were unfair to Africa, as they seemed to clearly undermine African interests and exhibited unwillingness to make concessions and held rigidly to their own demands.

Following from the above, this article examined Nigeria's major continental rivals in the quest to secure a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council (UNSC). In doing so, I conducted a comparative analysis of some of the strengths and weaknesses of Nigeria's core co-contenders alongside Nigeria to expose some of the major limiting factors that will make Nigeria's quest for a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council unlikely. Therefore, this article focused on Nigeria's perceived rivals in its quest for a permanent seat in the UNSC. The following analysis analyzed the potential and challenges on the path of continental rivals, including Egypt, Kenya, and South Africa, as they battle for a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council.

Egypt

Egypt's historical and geo-strategic location has been one of the factors that have made it attractive to major superpowers since the partition and division of Africa among European countries.⁸ As Morgenthau argued, a state's geo-strategic location constitutes one of its major components of national power.⁹ It is based on the above line of thought that the superpowers perceive Egypt's location as important to their strategic interest in the Middle East and would stop at nothing to offer it the desired support as the quest for a permanent seat in the UNSC continues. Apart from its access to the Red Sea and the Pacific Ocean, Egypt serves as a major sea route to Asia and a bridge between Africa and the Middle East.¹⁰

While Egypt has been a serious source of conflict among superpowers during the colonial era and even the Cold War period¹¹, the nature of Egyptian foreign policy after the Cold War has witnessed a continuous closeness with the West, especially the United States.¹² As Egwu noted, a closer look at Egyptian relations with the West points to overwhelming support and military aid from the West, especially during the regime of the former dictator, Husni Mubarak, who was ousted from power after the 2011 revolution.¹³ Yet Egypt's close engagement with the West has continued even after the Islamic Brotherhood was overturned in a widely condemned coup.

Deducing from the analysis of Egypt's close political and military relations with the West, some foreign policy analysts such as Kuziemko and Werker argued that Western nations will favor Egypt in the event of any attempt

⁶These states include Brazil, Germany, India, and Japan.

⁷These states include Italy, Pakistan, Mexico, Argentina, Canada, Colombia, Costa Rica, Malta, the Republic of Korea, and San Marino

⁸Tonkuş, Selen. *Syria's foreign policy toward Israel* Middle East Technical University, Turkey, 2013.

⁹Mackenzie, John. *The Partition of Africa: And European Imperialism 1880-1900*. Routledge, 2005.

¹⁰Morgenthau, H., & *Politics Among Nations*. "The struggle for power and peace." *Nova York, Alfred Kopf* (1948).

¹¹Stohl, Péter Miletics–Róbert. "Quest for Egypt's Renewed Geopolitical Status." *The Dynamics of Conflicts in Africa in the Early 21st Century* 85 (2017).

¹²Hahn, P. L. (1991). *The United States, Great Britain, and Egypt, 1945-1956: Strategy and diplomacy in the early Cold War*. UNC Press Books, 1991.

¹³Dunn, Michael Collins. "US relations with Egypt: An overview." *Handbook of US-Middle East Relations* (2014): 281-293.

¹⁴Egwu, S. G. (2026). Interview by Ponsah Saleh, Jos, February 19, 2026.

to enlarge the permanent Security Council to encompass Africa.¹⁴ Thus, based on their argument from the above position, one commentator further argued that

Egypt will stand taller than other contenders in Africa because, unlike other countries, it serves two interests: the African region and the Islamic Arab interest. Apart from Nigeria's skilled and industrial military advantage over other African countries, Nigeria's multiple advantages make it unlikely for it to stand against Egypt's quest to secure a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council.¹⁵

While Selim offered a geo-strategic explanation of Egypt's advantage over other contenders¹⁶ like Nigeria, Macqueen offered a cultural-cum-religious sentiment.¹⁷ To Macqueen, Egypt's quest to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC is born out of the need to fill in the existing gap and lack of Arab and Islamic world representation.¹⁸ Thus, its aspiration should be viewed as a matter of international justice.

Regardless of the case, contemporary events in Egypt stand negating the earlier explanations by pro-Egyptian policymakers. This is because of the humiliation that saw Morsi's popularly elected government overturned by the military, which has continued to enjoy great political relevance in Egyptian history. The various protests and shaky security situation within the domestic front serves to deter any support Egypt may have enjoyed in its quest to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC.

However, the concern is whether Nigeria's political and security challenges are any better than those of Egypt. In recent times, Nigeria has been enmeshed in serious security challenges that have attracted condemnation. In addition, there are various development challenges, such as governance and corruption. These and more have made even Nigerian commentators oppose the country's aspiration to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC. Listen to one of Nigeria's most popular academics:

"Instead of the corrupt political elites concentrating on resolving some of the many challenges facing the country, such as bad governance, insecurity, and rising youth unemployment, they seem to be deeply concerned with the quest to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC. This is a clear case of missed priority."¹⁹

Yet even Ghana, its close partner, has often toured the same position with Nigeria at the multilateral level, and has been reported as opposing its quest to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC. Listen to one of the Ghanaian commentators:

"Ghana would wish to support the Nigerians' quest for a permanent seat, but we are aware of the aspirations of better candidates, such as Egypt and South Africa. Therefore, to stand with Nigeria merely because of our long history of friendship will be a great disservice to Africa. It will be in Ghana's interest to support reputable candidates that will make Africa proud in the community of nations."²⁰

A critical look at the above statement shows that Nigeria's bad reputation, even within its sub-region, has a negative implication on its aspiration to the UNSC seat. This factor, accompanied by its dwindling role and value

¹⁵ Kuziemko, Ilyana, and Eric Werker. "How much is a seat on the Security Council worth? Foreign aid and bribery at the United Nations." *Journal of political economy* 114, no. 5 (2006): 905-930.

¹⁶Maqari, Sheikh Ibrahim Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, January 10, 2026.

¹⁷Selim, Gamal M. "The international dimensions of democratization in Egypt." *Switzerland: Springer International Publishing* (2015).

¹⁸Macqueen, Benjamin. "Muslim states and reform of the United Nations Security Council." *Journal of Middle Eastern and Islamic Studies (in Asia)* 4, no. 3 (2010): 47-64, 2010.

¹⁹Macqueen, Benjamin. "Muslim states and reform of the United Nations Security Council." P. 48.

²⁰ Osoba, Segun O. "Corruption in Nigeria: historical perspectives." *Review of African political economy* 23, no. 69 (1996): 371-386.

²¹Seidu, Douglas. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Lagos, 14th January, 2026.

within the sub-region, would convince even cynics that Nigeria may not realize its quest for a permanent seat in the UNSC.

In conclusion, Egypt's recent political instability may have sent a bad signal to its African and Western allies and thus raised some questions about her quest for an international assignment such as the UNSC. However, Nigeria's bleak image crisis and domestic contradictions raise more questions about a better candidate for such a prestigious task. While Nigeria's challenge is further compounded by an unresolved national question as many ethnic groups are threatening the division of the country into many parts, Egypt's dilemma, though quite challenging, is minor when compared to Nigeria, and when resolved, it will help throw the country back into the top echelon of political power in the African region.

Republic of Kenya

The Republic of Kenya, one of East Africa's most unstable countries yet a pivotal leader, has been at the forefront of the quest to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC.²¹ However, no major Kenyan foreign policy statement has been found to be silent on the bias and uneven posture of the international distribution of power. Most of the contemporary Kenyan administrations, including the present one, have been radical in posture and have always advocated for the reform of the UNSC and other international bodies, such as the ICC.²²

It was out of the conviction that Kenyan policymakers have been seen to be proactive in their quest to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC. Listen to the former Minister of East African Regional Cooperation:

"In Kenya, we believe in a just and equitable world. In this light, our quest for a permanent seat in the UNSC should be supported by all African states who see the clear lack of representation of the African continent in the body that aspires to maintain peace and security of all. Our contributions in maintaining peace and security in the East African sub-region and other parts of Africa should be acknowledged, and Kenya is ready to contest for the permanent seats of the UNSC with any country that claims to have any credentials."²³

The above statement shows that Kenya claims to have unmatched credentials from her engagement in ensuring international peace and security, and that it is one of the major prerequisites for any country seeking to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC. Following the above, the article examined Kenya's role in maintaining peace and security within both the Eastern African sub-region and the African region in general.

Kenya is viewed by the international community as a crusader against international crime and terrorism, at least in the East African sub-region.²⁴ Successive administrations in Kenya have maintained anti-terrorist positions in their national legislations, and this has earned Kenya a lot of applause among the Commonwealth members.²⁵ Kenya's resolve to fight terrorism stemmed from her bitter experience in the late 1990s, specifically in 1998, when Al-Qaeda attacked the United States embassies in Nairobi and Tanzania, the Kenyan capital.²⁶ Thus, the

²² Aronson, Samuel L. "United States aid to Kenya: A study on regional security and counterterrorism assistance before and after 9/11." *African journal of criminology and justice studies* 5, no. 1 (2011): 10.

²³(Okuta, 2013).

²⁴Salaitei, S. N., Rashid, S., Muthoni, and Kocrup Makuach Aleu. "Kenya's candidate for a non-permanent seat on the UNSC: An Assessment of Contributions, Priorities and Challenges." *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences* 8 (2019): 1-16.

²⁶Otiso, Kefa. "Kenya in the crosshairs of global terrorism: Fighting terrorism at the periphery." *Kenya Studies Review* 1, no. 1 (2009): 107-132.

²⁷Ekanem, E. A., & Asukwo, and Ekanem Asukwo. "Al Shabaab and its violent extremism in Kenya." *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 7, no. 5 (2022): 188-204.

1998 event and the ensuing closer partnership with the United States projected Kenya's anti-terrorism status to that of a global campaigner against such heinous crimes against humanity.

This has also helped bolster Kenya's regional status. However, Kenya's fight against terrorism (Al-Shabaab and Al-Qaeda) has not yielded the desired results, as seen in the recent gruesome attack by Al-Shabaab, a Somali terrorist group with links to Al-Qaeda (Wishart, 2013). In addition, in most cases, the victims of such attacks were either Western tourists or fellow African visitors; thus, it has always attracted international media attention (Bianchi, 2006). Kidnaping for ransom and activities of Somali pirates have always been the major source of Kenya's engagement, and there have been significant improvements until the recent attack that raised doubts about Kenya's security strategy against terrorists. The BBC blamed Al-Shabaab's lack of coherent coordination and dearth of intelligence gathering as the window exploited by the government (BBC, 2013).

However, is Nigeria any better in areas where Kenya is seen to be lacking? A comparative analysis of the many terrorist threats against the Nigerian state and Kenya shows a sharp contrast. While there are serious allegations against some top government officials as supporters of such serious security challenges that threaten the very foundation of the Nigerian state, the Kenyan government has shown some sense of responsibility by responding with caution, even though it is not good enough to prevent the attack from being carried out. At least from a study of what has been reported, the Nigerian situation is a homegrown terrorism that has grown out of a cycle of dissatisfaction with poor governance and has posed real threats to the government of the day without any serious action to stem the rising tide. The case in Kenya appears to be an exogenous reaction to the assault on Al-Shabaab. While it has been obvious over the course of 2013 that they have been involved in increasingly sophisticated attacks, Kenya continues to attract respect among nations for her resilience in the fight against terrorism. The point made therefore is the fact that in spite of Nigeria's condemnation after every terrorist attack, as contended in government official statements, it has not done enough to quell the situation and has further inflamed international criticism and methods of engagement often employed by the establishment. This has further dampened the country's image crisis in the international cycle.

Unlike Nigeria, Kenya's image and her dogged stand and commitments toward the fight against terrorist networks in the East Africa sub-region have been acknowledged by the United Nations in recent times. This is what the UN information department must say:

“The United Nations wishes to acknowledge the contribution of successive Kenyan administrations in the fight against terrorism in the entire East African sub-region in strong terms. Kenya has shown high-level commitment and sacrifice in its quest to end the provocation of pirates and terrorists. “The world body will continue to collaborate with Kenya in the fight against crime and terrorism.”²⁷

The ongoing prosecution of Kenya's president and vice president by the ICC on allegations of three judicial killings in the aftermath of the 2007 election raises other problematic questions about Kenya's reputation and unresolved issues of bad governance. However, as argued by Clark, many African governments and the African Union in particular have questioned the credibility of the ICC as most victims of such prosecutions have been seen to be from the continent.²⁸ In short, most African governments see the body as a neo-colonial court that seeks to reduce the sovereignty of states against the Founding Charter of the United Nations, especially UN Article 2, paragraph 7 of the UN Charter, which reads: “Nothing contained in the present charter, shall authorize the UN to

²⁸UNID, 2013:

²⁹Clark, Phil. *Distant Justice: The Impact of the International Criminal Court on African Politics* Cambridge University Press, 2018.

intervene in matters which are essentially within the domestic jurisdiction of any state, or shall require the members to submit such matters to settlement under the present charter.”²⁹

Thus, the negative effects that one expects to ordinarily accompany the prosecution of a sitting president and vice president of Kenya by the ICC, which seeks to join the permanent members of the United Nations Security Council, have attracted great sympathy among countries that have always had a hangover of deep historical wounds from the colonial period and the feeling of continued exploitation by the global hegemonic powers.

Drawing from the above analysis, Kenya’s quest for a permanent seat in the UNSC will likely enjoy maximum support given its smooth relations with both African and Western nations. As captured in the analysis of Kenya’s foreign relations, Kenya is more admired within the diplomatic community than some African countries, including Nigeria.³⁰

In conclusion, Kenya’s attractiveness in the international community coupled with its admirable reputation as a tourist state would not only appeal to other countries, but it is highly unlikely that Nigeria will defeat Kenya if the enlargement of the UNSC debate is eventually put to vote, either within the African Union or the more inclusive General Assembly of the UN.

South Africa

Of all the other African co-contenders for the permanent seat in the UNSC, the Republic of South Africa poses more threats to Nigeria than Egypt and Kenya. In short, the Nigerian Ministry of Foreign Affairs and other national think-tanks on foreign affairs, such as the Nigerian Institute for International Affairs and the Nigerian Institute for Policy and Strategic Studies (NIPSS), have been more concerned with countering South Africa’s diplomatic strength than any of the other two countries.³¹

This cannot be separated from South Africa’s penchant for struggle for space in both the African region and the global South, and after the collapse of minority rule in 1994, relations between the two countries soured.³² To understand the basis of the ensuing analysis and arguments, the article explained the beginning of the diplomatic crisis between South Africa and Nigeria.

With the accession of multi-racial democracy in South Africa under Nelson Mandela, Nigeria’s military government, headed by General Abacha, met with strong political opposition to its dictatorship within both Africa and the international institutional framework.³³ While the Abacha regime saw the South African government as acting on Western scripts, as indicated in the regime’s Minister of Information’s criticism of Mandela as a ‘black president of a white country,’ the South African government, on the other hand, felt that the Abacha regime was a disgrace to the African region, especially when the country was turning into a rogue state, with the execution of Ken Saro Wiwa and eight others.³⁴ The diplomatic crisis between these two giant states grew larger in scale with

³⁰UN Art. 2, Para. 7.

³¹Adeniji, Abolade. "Power and representation at the United Nations: A critique of Nigeria's bid for permanent seat in the Security Council." *India Quarterly* 61, no. 2 (2005): 116-137.

³²Adebajo, Adekeye, and Christopher Landsberg. "South Africa and Nigeria as regional hegemons." *From Cape to Congo: Southern Africa's evolving security challenges* (2003): 171-203.

³³Black, David. "The New South Africa confronts Abacha's Nigeria: The politics of human rights in a seminal relationship." *Commonwealth & Comparative Politics* 41, no. 2 (2003): 35-54.

³⁴Vale, Peter, and Sipho Maseko. "South Africa and the African renaissance." *International affairs* 74, no. 2 (1998): 271-287.

the suspension of Nigeria from the Commonwealth organization in 1995 in Auckland, New Zealand, led by South Africa.³⁵

Until General Abdulsalam came to power after General Sani Abacha died, Nigeria was almost “silent” in global affairs and was a rogue state in most instances.”³⁶ It is important to note that before South Africa’s emergence from the apartheid regime, Nigeria was seen as the Giant of Africa and was always shouldering the leadership responsibility in virtually most of the issues that concern the continent, from decolonization to the fight against minority rule, including the fight against African marginalization in international organizations.”

While widely regarded scholars like Mazrui and Karioki have offered colonial views in their quest to explain Nigeria’s relations with South Africa³⁷, the real reason seems to lie in the behavior of nation states in trying to project and maximize their national interest; states continually fight among themselves as a means to achieving their national interest. This quest to maximize their national objective principally explains Nigeria’s diplomatic disputes with South Africa and other countries in Africa. It would be misleading to argue that aside from national interest, there are other reasons that can adequately explain Nigeria-South Africa bitter relations.

The contention between the two giants of the African region in contemporary times can be explained in terms of “the quest by both countries to secure permanent seats in the UNSC.” The quest of both countries to achieve this lofty objective has resulted in mutual suspicion and execrable relations in recent times.”³⁸

For example, in March 2012, the Nigerian government, through its Foreign Affairs Ministry, accused its South African counterpart of xenophobia when the latter expelled over 125 Nigerian citizens on a negligible issue that was considered to be a yellow card. In response, Nigeria quietly did the same thing until the latter reversed its decision. Although both countries have established strong and vibrant bi-national commissions and have entered into many forms of agreement, private citizens of both countries still suspect one another via a sort of Cold War.³⁹ This shameful act by Africa’s most influential states raises questions about whether Africa will ever agree to present consensus candidates in the event of the United Nations Security Council enlargements.

Yet, while many observers of Nigeria-South Africa relations viewed the continued bitter relations and mutual suspicion as a manifestation of the quest to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC, only a few scholars see the overwhelming advantages South Africa has over Nigeria.

To start with, the large size of South Africa’s economy, combined with its multiracial composition, coupled with its historic emergence from the apartheid regime to the admiration of the world, has always attracted a combination of respect and prestige within Africa and the world.⁴⁰ A South African policymaker claimed the following on the issue of a permanent seat in the UNSC:

“South Africa has prepared its muscles for such international responsibility. We are more politically, militarily, economically, and socially stable than any other African country. Our economy is viral and strategically placed to perform this duty to the admiration of all.”⁴¹

³⁵Carmody, Chi. "On Expelling Nigeria from the Commonwealth." *Canadian Yearbook of International Law/Annuaire canadien de droit international* 34 (1996): 273-291.

³⁶Johnson, Idire. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 7th February, 2026.

³⁷Mazrui, Ali Al’ Amin, and James N. Karioki. "A tale of two Africas: Nigeria and South Africa as contrasting visions." (*No Title*) (2006).

³⁸Adewale, Abiodun. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 28th March, 2026.

³⁹Eigbefoh, E. S. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 16th March, 2026.

⁴⁰Schraeder, Peter J. “South Africa’s foreign policy: From international pariah to leader of the African renaissance.” *Commonwealth Journal of International Affairs and Policy Issues*, pp. 57-76. Volume 90, 2001, Issue 359, 2001

⁴¹Masingie, Mafemani. Interview with Ponsah Saleh, Abuja, 15th January, 2026.

However, Nigeria has always prided itself as the chief contributor to the various liberation struggles in Africa, and South Africa is one of the many beneficiaries of its gestures. Thus, South Africa will be unthankful for opposing Nigeria's ambition in the race to secure a permanent seat in the UNSC.

Again, South Africa's economy has recorded huge successes accentuated with China's penetration, making it the largest economy in the African region.⁴² To add to this, it has some of the best universities in the region, which has produced large-scale business entrepreneurs. All these points point to the fact that South Africa can shoulder huge responsibility in the region, as compared to Nigeria, which is fast relapsing in international engagement. Thus, it will be highly unlikely for fellow African countries to support Nigeria's quest. The South African High Commissioner to Nigeria summarized this in the following manner:

"Unlike many of our co-contenders, we have, over the years, been catering to our fellow African countries, owing them arrears from international organizations, including the UN. This has placed us above our rivals, and our recent victory over our rivals within the AU gives a clear picture of our acceptance in Africa and what will likely be."⁴³

The above statement is a diplomatic pointer to Nigeria's support for a candidate who was defeated in the recent AU chairperson election won by South African candidates. Nigeria's credentials undermine those of South Africa regarding issues of active engagement in maintaining peace and security in the region. While Nigeria has a record of participating in over 27 United Nations peacekeeping operations, South Africa has not been very visible in this area, especially with a long history of apartheid rule. However, it seems the country has started aggressive engagements in the African region, and its presence has been felt in most of the hot spots in Africa. Yet it seems Nigeria's engagement in the African region has been drastically challenged by domestic pressure, and the rise of countries like South Africa has further undermined her previous role and perceived relevance.

Moreover, while both countries face deep security challenges at the domestic level (South Africa's high-profile crime rates and Nigeria's homegrown terrorism), Nigeria's challenges far outweigh South Africa's security challenges. South Africa's crime rate has not deterred South Africa's performances at the sub-regional or regional level, unlike Nigeria, where the country's sub-regional and regional influence seems to be sinking, combined with rigorous development challenges.

Furthermore, in pressing for support from fellow Black African countries, General Obasanjo, Nigeria's former president, advanced the claim that South Africa is a white-dominated country and Egypt is a yellow-dominant one. Thus, the real African country, in the true sense of the word, is Nigeria, which is home to the world's largest concentration of blacks.

Unfortunately, the African common position, or the Ezulwini Consensus, has no regard for black, white, or yellow Africa, and it would be a huge diplomatic miscalculation for Nigeria to play a racial card or provoke the mind of fellow African countries whose diversity or racial composition is a matter of historical accident. This particular reasoning is not representative of Nigeria, a country whose former leaders are celebrated as true African patriots who fought for the liberation of virtually all countries, regardless of region, race, religion, or color. After all, this line of reasoning was viewed as mockery and can at best attract sympathy for the so-called white or yellow African countries.

Conclusion

⁴² Enaifoghe, Andrew O., Anita O. Aina, and Anuoluwapo A. Durokifa. "South Africa's economic progress: Challenges and opportunities for sustainable development." *International Journal of Development and Sustainability* 10, no. 9 (2021): 340-357.

⁴³ Mnguni and Lulu Louis

In conclusion, what is clear from the Nigerian loss at the level of the African Union is the fact that Nigeria's leadership in Africa has now received a credible threat with more countries developing fashion in engaging Nigeria even on the pages of newspapers apparently because of the downturn in Nigeria's image, profile, bad governance, corruption, poor leadership, and even a drop in international engagement. In sum, Egypt, Kenya, and South Africa seem to be better positioned going by both their contemporary, domestic, and continental relevance, and Nigeria's quest to secure a permanent seat in the United Nations will be unlikely to be realized in the presence of these viral contenders.

Drawing from the foregoing analysis of the aggressive campaign among African states, two likely results may be expected: it will be unlikely that Nigeria's quest to secure a permanent seat in the United Nations will be realized in the presence of inter-African rivalry from better-positioned states, or that the aggressive pursuit or quest among the pivotal leaders would make it unlikely for African countries to reach a common consensus on states that will represent her on the Security Council; thus, Africa will remain without a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council.

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